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Guidelines for Repository Providers - Improving Long-Term Preservation of Digital Research Data

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Executive summary

The long-term preservation of digital research data is a key component in moving towards a sustainable data culture in Earth System Sciences (ESS) and science in general. Digital long-term preservation entails the ability to preserve data in a way that ensures its authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability throughout technological and cultural change for as long as the data is required, potentially indefinitely. This requires designated curation institutions, in the case of research data these are normally subject-specific repositories, willing and capable to take over the responsibility for the data in the long term and to conduct preservation actions over time.

This document provides guidance and support for repository providers aiming to implement or improve on existing long-term preservation approaches for digital research data. On the one hand, these guidelines illustrate and raise awareness for the challenges of digital long-term preservation and solution approaches, existing conceptual standards and principles in this area as well as frameworks for trustworthy digital repositories. On the other hand, they offer abstract guidance for the decision-making process connected with the implementation of long-term preservation policies and strategies on an institutional level as well as workflows for the active preservation in repositories. The document is intended as an entry point to these topics, offering references to more detailed and in-depth resources on specific aspects of digital long-term preservation.

The primary target group of this document are stakeholders within repositories, e.g., decision-makers, repository managers, or expert staff, regardless of the repository's size or its current stage of digital preservation maturity. These guidelines are designed to support both established as well as smaller and emerging repository providers in developing and implementing pragmatic preservation strategies. Given that repositories are part of a wider ecosystem of digital research infrastructures and often dependent on external funding, this document might be also relevant for policy-makers and funders, engaged in shaping the overall landscape of digital infrastructures and data culture in science.

Abbreviations

AIP - Archival Information Package

CC - Creative Commons

CCSDS - Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems

DCC - Digital Curation Centre

DIN - German Institute for Standardization (Deutsches Institut für Normung)

DIP - Dissemination Information Package

DPC - Digital Preservation Coalition

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud

ESS - Earth System Sciences

FAIR - FAIR Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

IPR - Intellectual Property Rights

ISO - International Organization for Standardization

M2.4 - NFDI4Earth Measure 2.4 Data in Long-Term Storage

NFDI - National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur)

NFDI4Earth - NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences (NFDI Konsortium Erdsystemforschung)

OAIS - Open Archival Information System

PID - Persistent Identifier

PREMIS - PREservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies

RDM - Research Data Management

SIP - Submission Information Package

TDR - Trustworthy Digital Repository

TRUST - TRUST Principles: Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, Technology

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1 Introduction

A key component in moving towards a sustainable data culture in Earth System Sciences (ESS) and science in general, is to secure the preservation of relevant research data in the long term. While in many scientific disciplines a retention timeframe for research data of ten years¹ has been established, digital long-term preservation aims at ensuring the authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability of data throughout technological and cultural changes over time, potentially indefinitely. In the NFDI4Earth measure M2.4 "Data in Long-Term Storage" we develop and provide materials and guidelines for the improvement of long-term preservation of ESS data, aiming to facilitate an easy to understand entry point to relevant aspects on this topic.

Long-term preservation of digital data can be accomplished successfully only within a designated curation institution willing to take over the responsibility for the data in the long term. In the case of research data, these designated curation institutions are normally subject-specific or institutional repositories, willing and capable to fulfill this role.² It is important to be aware that securing the preservation of digital data in the long term, potentially indefinitely, requires the allocation of significant resources in a sustainable way. Furthermore, not every repository might have the need and/or the resources to offer long-term preservation services.³

The goal of these "Guidelines for repository providers" is to provide guidance for repository providers aiming to implement a coherent long-term preservation approach for digital research data or improve on existing preservation approaches, strategies, workflows, etc. On the one hand, these guidelines aim to illustrate and raise awareness for the challenges of digital long-term preservation and solution approaches, existing conceptual standards and principles in this area as well as frameworks for trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs). On the other hand, these guidelines intend to offer abstract guidance for the decision-making process connected with the implementation of long-term preservation policies and strategies as well as workflows for the active preservation of digital objects in repositories. Digital preservation is often a continuous maturity process rather than an immediate commitment to complex standards. For smaller repositories, starting with pragmatic and modular steps (e.g., ensuring bitstream integrity) can provide a good foundation for further development and gradual improvement.

The implementation of a coherent long-term preservation approach for digital research data depends on many variables, e.g., what type of data and file formats are being accepted by the repository, the choice of preservation strategies and levels of preservation offered, for

¹ In accordance with the "Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice" from the DFG, see: (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, 2022)

² (Andreu, et al., 2023); (L'Hours, et al., 2022)

³ (Paul-Stüve, Schürmann, & Valena, 2024)

which user community the data is being preserved, etc. To put it simply, in digital long-term preservation there is no one-size-fits-all solution. Thus, these guidelines aim to serve as an entry point on the topic and to potential pitfalls of digital long-term preservation in repositories, providing references to more detailed and in-depth resources on specific aspects of digital long-term preservation in repositories.

The primary target group of these guidelines are all relevant stakeholders, expert staff, and decision-makers in repositories for research data, dealing with aspects of digital long-term preservation. Since repositories for research data are part of a wider ecosystem of digital research infrastructures and often dependent on funding by external stakeholders, these guidelines can be relevant also for policy-makers, decision-makers, and funders, engaged in shaping the overall landscape of digital infrastructures and data culture in science.

The guidelines will cover relevant aspects of the data life cycle for the preservation of digital research data from the point onwards it is being offered to the repository. The focus will be on long-term preservation of digital research data in repositories. General repository operations as well as the long-term preservation of (research) software will not be explicitly covered in these guidelines. For geospatial data created by governmental agencies, further domain-specific national frameworks and legal regulations might apply, specifying responsibilities, formal criteria (e.g., file format, metadata), and workflows for its long-term preservation.⁴

2 Basics about Digital Long-Term Preservation⁵

Understanding the challenges of preserving digital data in the long term, the overarching objectives of digital long-term preservation, different solution approaches, and strategies dealing with the challenges of preserving digital data, is essential for the conceptualization and implementation of a functioning long-term preservation policy. This chapter provides a concise introduction to what digital long-term preservation is about.

2.1 Digital Obsolescence

For digital data to be human- and machine-readable, a software environment is required that correctly interprets the information encoded in a specific file format as well as renders and presents its content. Software environments, in turn, require an operating system that they can run on. The operating system supports and manages a particular system infrastructure that is implemented in a hardware environment. All these components, hardware and software

⁴ See e.g.: (Würriehausen, et al., 2021); (AdV-KLA-Arbeitsgruppe "Archivierung von Geobasisdaten", 2021); national and federal state archival laws.

⁵ Adapted from (Valena & Schürmann, 2024); (Valena & Schmalzl, 2024); (Wieshuber, 2025)

environments, operating systems, as well as file formats in use, are subject to continuous technological and cultural change, being at risk of becoming obsolete at some point in the future. This poses the risk of losing access to the content of digital data, leaving it unusable and unintelligible. Addressing and coping with these risks of digital obsolescence is the main challenge in preserving digital data in the long term.⁶

2.2 Goals and Objectives

Digital long-term preservation can be defined as “a series of managed activities necessary to ensure continued access to digital materials, or at least to the information contained in them, indefinitely”.⁷ The aim is to ensure the (re)usability, comprehensibility, and trustworthiness of digital data over an extended period of time, potentially indefinitely, through securing the authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability of digital data over time.

In regard to digital long-term preservation,

- **authenticity** refers to the evidence-based assurance that a digital object is what it claims to be and has not been altered in an unauthorized way. This requires maintaining reliable metadata and documentation about the digital object’s context of creation, provenance, chain of custody, and any preservation actions undertaken over time.
- **integrity** means the guarantee that the digital object remains complete, unaltered, and accurate over time. This is being accomplished by protecting the digital object from corruption, loss, or unauthorized changes with the help of mechanisms such as checksums and fixity checks.
- **access** refers to the ability to reliably retrieve and render the content of the digital object for ongoing usage, retaining its authenticity and functionality throughout changes in technology that occur over time.
- **interpretability** refers to the ability to semantically understand the content of the digital object in the future. It requires metadata and documentation about the context, structure, and meaning of the content of the digital object.

2.3 Levels of Preservation and Preservation Strategies

There are different strategies and approaches dealing with the various aspects of the challenges of digital obsolescence and securing the authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability of

⁶ For a concise description regarding the perception and rendering of digital data, its dependencies on soft- and hardware environments, as well as its ramifications for the preservation of digital data, see: (National Archives of Australia, 2002)

⁷ (Digital Preservation Coalition, 2015, p. glossary)

digital data. The Levels of Preservation Matrix, developed by the National Digital Stewardship Alliance (NDSA), offers a helpful overview on different levels of preservation across several functional areas.⁸

2.3.1 Bitstream Preservation

The objective of bitstream (or bit-level) preservation is to maintain an unaltered physical copy of the digital object, ensuring its integrity over time. It refers to methods, approaches, and strategies to ensure the preservation of the exact bit string (sequence of 0s and 1s) of the digital object. Risks to the preservation of the digital object on a bitstream level include data degradation (also bit rot or data decay) over time, accidental and intentional alterations, or disasters threatening to physically damage or destroy the storage facility, such as e.g., fire, floods, earthquakes.

Methods to cope with these risks include:

- **Fixity checks, data checks, and monitoring:** Fixity refers to the assurance that a digital object remains unchanged over time. A fixity check determines if an object has been altered without authorization and documentation or has become corrupted. In most cases, checksum algorithms are used for this purpose. These algorithms normally use cryptographic hash functions to ensure that two different digital objects do not produce the same checksum (= collision resistance). The checksum or cryptographic hash of a digital object can be stored in the preservation metadata. To keep data fixity over time, regular monitoring and data checks are required.
- **Redundant storage and multiple copies:** According to the 3-2-1 rule, it is recommended to keep at least three independent copies on two different types of storage media, with one copy located offsite. Maximizing storage diversification helps to minimize the exposure to specific risks and threats to the preservation on a bitstream level.
- **Storage media migration:** To avoid the growing risks to bitstream integrity on ageing storage media becoming less reliable or obsolete, regular migration to newer storage media is required.

Bitstream preservation is mostly concerned with the mere storage of a digital object and ensuring its integrity on the bitstream level. Bitstream preservation can be seen as a basic requirement and prerequisite for the long-term preservation of digital data, by itself though it does not ensure the preservation of the content of a digital object and its authentic meaning throughout technological and cultural changes over time.

⁸ <https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

2.3.2 Content Preservation

Content preservation on the other hand addresses the challenges and risks of digital obsolescence in a comprehensive way, offering solutions and strategies to ensure that the content of a digital object remains accessible, usable, authentic, and understandable throughout technological and cultural changes over time. There are two main approaches that offer solutions to the risk of losing access to the content of a digital object due to the obsolescence of file formats, software, and operating systems over time.

The migration strategy ensures continuous access to the content of the original digital object as well as the ability to render its content through migration to newer file formats, once the currently used file format is in danger of becoming technically obsolete or getting out of use, creating a new representation of the original digital object's underlying intellectual entity. This requires ongoing monitoring of technological and cultural changes in order to determine the point in time when preservation actions need to be undertaken. Migrating the content of a digital object to a newer file format can lead to a loss of information, appearance, or functionality in comparison to the original digital object. Defining the essential characteristics (referred to as "Significant Properties"⁹) of the digital object that needs to be preserved over time, helps to select the most suitable file format for the specific digital object to be migrated to.

The emulation strategy on the other hand, keeps the original digital object as it is and aims at ensuring continuous access to its content through (re)creating the original software environment, which the digital object was intended to run on, on to newer hardware environments and operating systems. This allows preserving the original functionalities of the digital object as well as avoiding the risk of information loss during migration to newer file formats. It can be challenging though to create emulators due to technical and legal issues, especially for proprietary file formats and software environments. Emulation requires freely accessible and usable comprehensive documentation about the source code and structure of the respective file format of the digital object and the software environment it was intended to run on. Significant properties are also required for verifying the functionality of the newly created emulator.

In addition, for full preservation (sometimes also referred to as semantic preservation) ensuring authenticity and interpretability on a semantic level of the digital object is required. This entails preserving documentation and descriptive metadata on a conceptual level about the digital object, such as information about e.g., the context, structure, provenance, methodology, as well as interdependencies and relationships to other digital objects and resources. This documentation and metadata need to be monitored and, if required, regularly updated depending on the changing user expectations over time.

⁹ (Wilson, 2018); (National Archives and Records Administration (NARA), 2009); (PREMIS Editorial Committee, 2015, pp. 50-55)

3 Principles and Standards for Digital Long-Term Preservation

Regarding how a successful long-term preservation of digital data can be accomplished there have been various standards and principles established, applicable also as a conceptual framework for the long-term preservation of digital research data. This chapter provides a contextualization of the FAIR principles in regard to digital long-term preservation as well as an overview of the Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS), and the standard Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies (PREMIS) as the most relevant and widespread conceptual frameworks on digital long-term preservation.

3.1 FAIR Principles

The FAIR principles¹⁰ have established themselves as guiding principles for the stewardship of digital research data and research data management (RDM) in the scientific domain. While the FAIR principles do not explicitly address long-term preservation and are not considered a preservation standard per se, they nevertheless play an important role in the long-term preservation of digital research data. Research data that has been made FAIR typically adheres to established and well-documented community standards and contains a high degree of contextual information about the digital object captured in standardized metadata schemas (e.g., DataCite). These aspects contribute significantly to the ability to preserve its authenticity and interpretability on a semantic level as well as conduct preservation actions in a designated curation institution in the long term.

It is important to be aware that the FAIRness of research data (the digital object itself as well as its metadata) left unattended may decrease over time. Research data that has been made FAIR according to today's standards might not be FAIR anymore in the future. Technologies, standards, expectations from the user community, etc. all change over time, affecting the degree of FAIRness of research data. Thus, keeping research data FAIR requires ongoing monitoring of cultural and technological changes as well as undertaking adequate preservation and curation actions by the repository as the designated curation institution.¹¹

The FAIR principles focus primarily on characteristics of the data object and its metadata, required for research data to be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Nevertheless, for the data to be made FAIR, also supporting infrastructures, such as repositories for research data, must align their services according to the FAIR principles.

Extensive resources on FAIR-enabling practices and its implementation in repositories have been created within several projects funded by the European Union, such as "FAIRsFAIR -

¹⁰ (Wilkinson, et al., 2016); <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

¹¹ (Andreu, et al., 2023); (L'Hours, et al., 2022)

Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe”¹² or “EOSC FAIR-IMPACT - Expanding FAIR Solutions across EOSC”¹³. Furthermore, NFDI4Earth offers with the NFDI4Earth Label a semi-automated evaluation for assessing the FAIRness and especially the interoperability of repositories in ESS.¹⁴

3.2 Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS)

The Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS) is an abstract conceptual framework for the long-term preservation of digital information in a digital archive or repository. Originally developed by the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) for the long-term preservation of digital data from space missions, the OAIS evolved into a widely accepted and adopted de facto standard in digital preservation communities worldwide, serving as a reference framework for standards, concepts, and terminology on digital preservation.¹⁵ After a process of consultation with stakeholders from archives and libraries, it was published first in 2003 as an ISO-Standard (ISO 14721:2003) and recently published in an updated version (ISO 14721:2025).

An OAIS is defined as “an Archive system consisting of hardware, software, information, and policy-based processes and procedures put in place and operated by an organization and its staff. The organization has accepted the responsibility to preserve information and make it available for a Designated Community.”¹⁶ The two primary objectives are to preserve digital information in the long term throughout technological and cultural changes as well as to guarantee ongoing access to the preserved information for the user community. The following paragraphs provide a very concise overview of selected core elements of the OAIS, without any claim to completeness.

For repositories to be compliant with the OAIS reference model, the following **mandatory responsibilities**¹⁷ have to be assumed:

- Negotiate for and accept appropriate information from the information producer

¹² <https://fairsfair.eu/> (accessed: 10 December 2025); for project outputs, see the Zenodo-Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/fairsfair> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

¹³ <https://fair-impact.eu/> (accessed: 10 December 2025); for project outputs, see the Zenodo-Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-impact> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

¹⁴ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/label> (accessed: 10 December 2025); (Schäfer, et al., 2024)

¹⁵ (Lavoie, 2014, p. 5)

¹⁶ (The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, 2024b, p. 1-1)

¹⁷ In more detail see, (The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, 2024b, pp. 3-1 to 3-7); (Lavoie, 2014, p. 7)

- Obtain sufficient control of the information for the purpose of fulfilling long-term preservation objectives
- Determine the user community (“designated community”) and their knowledge base
- Ensure that the information being preserved is independently understandable to the determined user community based on their knowledge base functionality
- Follow documented policies and procedures which ensure that the information is preserved against all reasonable contingencies
- Make the preserved information available to the determined user community and allow for the dissemination of authentic copies

3.2.1 OAIS Environment

The OAIS environment¹⁸ describes the relevant external stakeholders outside of the OAIS, with which the OAIS has to interact and cooperate in order to successfully preserve information in the long term and fulfill its responsibilities.

The OAIS environment consists of the following three external components:

- **Producers:** Producers are the external stakeholders who produce the information designated for long-term preservation as well as provide and transfer it to the OAIS. They can be individuals, organizations, or client systems. Interaction between the OAIS and the producers is typically formalized within submission agreements for the information to be preserved.
- **Consumers:** Consumers are the external stakeholders who use the information that is preserved and provided by the OAIS. Like the producers, consumers can be individuals, organizations, or client systems. The Designated Community is a specific class of consumers who are expected to independently understand the preserved information without the need for additional specialized resources or expert support. The definition of the scope of the designated community as well as the knowledge base of the designated community by the OAIS has therefore significant implications on the preservation planning within the OAIS, including the scope of required contextual information (e.g., in form of metadata) about the preserved data.
- **Management:** While not being involved in the day-to-day operations of the OAIS, management functions in an oversight capacity for the overall operations of the OAIS. It formulates and adapts as necessary the high-level policy framework of the OAIS, conducts strategic planning, and defines the scope of the collection policy. Management

¹⁸ In more detail see, (The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, 2024b, pp. 2-2 to 2-2)

over time, such as procedures e.g., for error checking, media refreshment, or format migration.

- **Data Management:** This entity is responsible for maintaining the internal databases of descriptive and administrative metadata, supporting the other functional entities in their services. This includes e.g., performing database updates (as needed), allowing for query requests and responses to be generated, or supporting the search for and retrieval of content.
- **Administration:** The primary task is to manage and to monitor the overall operations of the OAIS as well as to coordinate the activities of the other five functional entities in the OAIS. In addition, the administration interacts with external stakeholders, such as producers (e.g., regarding the negotiation of submission agreements), consumers, and management.
- **Preservation Planning:** The main responsibility of this entity is to design the overall preservation strategies and policies of the OAIS, to monitor the OAIS environment for changes in technology and user expectations as well as to recommend revisions to the preservation strategies, policies, and procedures addressing appropriately the changes in the OAIS environment. This includes e.g., the planning of format migration and risk analysis, aiming at securing the ability of the OAIS to meet its responsibilities for the data in the long term.
- **Access:** This entity functions as a link between the holdings of the OAIS and the consumer. It provides the services and interfaces for the consumer to search, request and receive information about the holdings of the OAIS as well as get access to the items in the archival storage. This includes, as needed, the transformation of the archived items into a format suitable for dissemination as well as implementing and maintaining access controls for restricted and sensitive data.

3.2.3 OAIS Information Model

The OAIS information model provides an abstract framework for managing information objects designated for long-term preservation in an OAIS-compliant repository. Centering around information packages, the information model defines how data is packaged and described in order to ensure its integrity, authenticity, and interpretability and thus its usability by the designated communities in the long term.

An information package consists of the following components:

- **Content information:** Contains the actual data (digital object) and its representation information. Representation information includes all required information to render and understand the digital object, based on the designated community's knowledge base.

- **Preservation description information:** Includes information required for the long-term preservation of the digital object, e.g., reference information, unique identifiers, provenance, context, fixity, and access rights.
- **Packaging information:** Is used to logically bind the different components of the information package together.
- **Descriptive information:** Supports the discovery and retrieval of the content information by the consumer.

The information model distinguishes between three different types of information packages:

- **Submission information package (SIP):** The SIP is the version that is transferred by the producers to the OAIS, normally based on the submission agreement.
- **Archival information package (AIP):** The AIP is the version that is stored and preserved in the OAIS. Depending on the information provided in the SIP, the AIP may have to be transformed (e.g., into a different file format) or enriched with additional information and metadata.
- **Dissemination information package (DIP):** The DIP is the version that is provided to the consumer.

The OAIS reference model provides an abstract high-level framework for the long-term preservation of digital information in a repository. While setting overall principles, the OAIS reference model does not stipulate a specific implementation or preservation strategy. This allows for various implementations of the OAIS reference model, depending on the specific needs and requirements of the repository and its user community, including taking into account organizational considerations and community standards.

Recommended further resources:

- Lavoie (2014): [The Open Archival Information System \(OAIS\) Reference Model: Introductory Guide](#)
- CCSDS (2024): [Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System \(OAIS\)](#)

3.3 Preservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies (PREMIS)

Preservation metadata is a fundamental component in the long-term management and preservation of digital objects in repositories. It refers to the information necessary to support the preservation process of digital data, ensuring the authenticity, integrity, access, and interpretability of the preserved data over time. At its core, preservation metadata includes information about the creation, management, and use of digital objects. The purpose of this metadata is not merely to document relevant information, but also action-oriented,

intended to support and document all ongoing preservation actions required over time throughout technological and cultural changes. This is a crucial cornerstone in maintaining trust, transparency, and accountability in the preservation process of digital data within repositories.

The most common and widely adopted standard for preservation metadata is **PREMIS (PREservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies)**²¹. Based on the OAIS reference model (especially the OAIS information model) and works from earlier working groups, the PREMIS Data Dictionary for Preservation Metadata was first published in 2005. Maintained and revised by the Library of Congress and the PREMIS editorial committee with representatives from the preservation community worldwide, the currently valid version 3.0 was published in 2015 and serves as a de facto international standard for preservation metadata.

The PREMIS Data Dictionary functions as a flexible framework for capturing core preservation metadata in a structured and standardized way, defining “things that most working preservation repositories are likely to need to know in order to support digital preservation.”²² PREMIS as a standard is technically neutral, making no assumptions about preservation strategies, technologies, metadata storage, etc., thus allowing interoperability, compatibility with other standards, and various ways of implementations, depending on the overall strategies and parameters deployed in the repository.

The PREMIS Data Dictionary is constituted around the PREMIS Data Model, which defines four entities (object, event, agent, rights) relevant for the digital preservation process and their relationships to each other. The specific pieces of information required about those four entities for the digital preservation process are defined and in detail described as semantic units.

Recommended further resources:

- Caplan (2021): [Understanding PREMIS](#)
- PREMIS Editorial Committee (2015): [PREMIS Data Dictionary for Preservation Metadata](#)
- [PREMIS website](#) (contains various documentations and supporting material for implementation)
- PREMIS Tutorial at iPres2022: Understanding and Implementing PREMIS: A Tutorial
 - [Slides of the presentation](#)
 - Recording of the tutorial, [Part 1](#) and [Part 2](#)

²¹ <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/> (accessed: 10 December 2025); (PREMIS Editorial Committee, 2015)

²² (PREMIS Editorial Committee, 2015, p. 3)

4 Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs)

A trustworthy digital repository is one whose policies, practices, and technology inspire confidence that it will safeguard digital data over the long term. In the digital preservation community and science, TDRs are widely recognized as essential for ensuring data integrity, authenticity, reliability and accessibility. In practice, trust is earned through transparent documentation of the repository's goals, responsibilities and capabilities. Over the past two decades, the community has developed audit criteria and standards (e.g., TRAC²³, ISO 16363²⁴) to define what makes a repository trustworthy. These frameworks encourage repositories to demonstrate their commitment to preservation by publishing policies, enabling external review, and aligning with established standards and principles such as the OAIS reference model. While such certifications provide a structured benchmark, their uptake varies. Some repositories are able to commit the necessary resources and gain credibility and community recognition through certification, while others cannot pursue this path due to the significant effort, cost, and staffing required. As a result, formal certification is not universal, yet the underlying criteria still shape good practice and are often applied even without obtaining a seal. The following sections discuss in more detail the dimensions of trustworthiness, the available certification frameworks and their practical implications, as well as recent European initiatives such as EOSC FIDELIS that seek to harmonize approaches across communities.

4.1 TRUST Principles for Repositories

To guide repository stewardship, the Research Data Alliance and World Data System formulated the TRUST principles²⁵: Transparency, Responsibility (sometimes called Accountability), User focus, Sustainability, and Technology. These abstract principles help stakeholders evaluate and compare repositories. Key points include:

- **Transparency:** TDRs must clearly communicate their mission, scope, services, and policies. For example, a trustworthy repository publishes its terms of use, selection criteria and preservation timeframe, so users can judge its suitability. Open documentation (e.g., online policies, metrics, evidence of preservation practices) builds confidence that the repository is operating honestly and verifiably.
- **Responsibility (Accountability):** TDRs take responsibility for stewarding their data holdings. This means following community metadata and curation standards, performing

²³ <https://catalog.crl.edu/Record/2d8d3782-5804-5962-9fd0-4dbd595a7eab> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

²⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/87472.html> (accessed: 10 December 2025); (The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, 2024a)

²⁵ (Lin, et al., 2020)

quality control, validating authenticity, and protecting intellectual property rights (IPR) and sensitive data. A TDR must have legal rights and staff workflows to manage deposits, ensure fixity of files, and plan for long-term access (e.g., assigning persistent identifiers, capturing sufficient metadata). Accountability may be supported by clear governance structures or legal mandates, assuring users that data will remain accessible and citable over time.

- **User Focus:** A TDR serves its target research community. It is embedded in community practices and adapts to evolving user needs. They make data findable and understandable (e.g., via community metadata and catalogs), encourage users to provide complete descriptive information, and facilitate reuse (e.g., by providing useful tools or interfaces). They also uphold relevant standards (e.g., formats, vocabularies, protocols) so that data interoperability and reusability are maximized.
- **Sustainability:** Continued access depends on funding, planning, and governance. TDRs demonstrate sustainability by planning for risk mitigation, disaster recovery, and succession as well as by securing long-term resources (e.g., staffing, hardware, legal support) to maintain services. Effective governance models (e.g., institutional policies or consortia agreements) ensure that valuable data remains discoverable and usable for future generations.
- **Technology (Technological Adequacy):** A TDR's technical infrastructure must reliably support preservation and access. This includes using appropriate, up-to-date standards, tools, and storage technologies for managing data and metadata. Repositories should have documented security measures and incident response plans to handle physical or cyber threats. In short, technical systems should fit the needs of the collections and be robust enough to deliver on the TRUST principles (e.g., protecting integrity and enabling recovery).

4.2 Certification and Audit Frameworks

Several formal frameworks exist to assess and certify repository trustworthiness. These provide checklists of requirements and external review processes. In Europe a tiered "framework for audit and certification" was originally intended. In practice, adoption is mixed: lightweight frameworks such as CoreTrustSeal are comparatively widespread, while more demanding audits like ISO 16363 are rare due to their cost and resource requirements. Certification can enhance credibility and user trust, but the preparation effort, documentation burden, and long review timelines often discourage institutions. The main frameworks relevant to data repositories are:

- **CoreTrustSeal (CTS)**²⁶: A community-driven certification (successor to the Data Seal of Approval) based on a concise set of requirements. All CTS requirements are mandatory and cover areas like organizational setup, data management, and technical infrastructure. Repositories self-assess against these requirements and submit evidence (e.g., policies, documentation, sample data) for peer review. Importantly, the CTS process is based on documented evidence rather than an onsite audit. Applicants make policy documents, workflows and other evidence publicly available, which “provides transparent assurance” of good practice. A CTS certification lasts three years, encouraging continuous improvement. CTS is well suited for scientific data repositories (e.g., many ICSU World Data System members use it) and represents a practical first step towards demonstrating trust.
- **ISO 16363 (Audit and certification of TDRs)**²⁷: An ISO standard that specifies a rigorous audit framework. ISO 16363 treats the entire organization as the unit of audit and defines over 100 measurable criteria grouped into three areas: Organizational infrastructure, digital object management, and infrastructure/environmental risk management. These criteria are built on the OAIS reference model and cover everything from governance, staffing and policies, through ingest and preservation planning, to security and disaster recovery. Compliance is assessed via a formal external audit (site visit and review by accredited auditors). Achieving ISO 16363 certification is a significant commitment (few repositories have completed it) and it provides the highest level of assurance of a repository’s trustworthiness.
- **DIN 31644 (nestor Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives)**²⁸: A German national standard (2012) for trustworthy digital archives. Its structure is similar to ISO 16363 but somewhat simpler. It defines requirements in three sections: the organizational framework (repository goals, designated community, legal and financial resources, etc.), object management (integrity and authenticity, preservation planning, metadata, packaging), and infrastructure/security (adequate IT systems). Although published in German, an English translation is available through the nestor network. Nestor (the German digital preservation network) offers a “nestor Seal” certification process based on DIN 31644 as an extended self-assessment. This process (taking a few months) helps repositories evaluate and improve their practices.

²⁶ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/> (accessed: 10 December 2025); (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2022)

²⁷ (The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, 2024a). This text is identical to the standard ISO 16363:2025.

²⁸ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/DE/Zertifizierung/nestor_Siegel/siegel.html (accessed: 10 December 2025); (nestor-Arbeitsgruppe Zertifizierung, 2024)

4.3 EOSC FIDELIS Project: Networking Trustworthy Repositories

Building on earlier certification efforts, European stakeholders have in recent years sought to complement individual audits with a coordinated network approach. The FIDELIS project (Horizon Europe, launched in 2025)²⁹ is building a European network of TDRs to underpin the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) ecosystem. Its goals are to harmonize definitions and practices of a repository's trustworthiness, develop and expand a community of trustworthy repositories, and to provide active support for upskilling repository staff. Within its three-year scope, FIDELIS will establish a self-sustaining network that tries to support the development and growth of TDRs in EOSC. Key objectives include fostering interoperability among repositories, aligning policies (in partnership with EOSC's EDEN project on preservation), and enhancing skills through training programs.

Core activities of the FIDELIS Network are stakeholder advocacy and engagement (serving as an advocacy group for FAIR-enabling, trustworthy repositories), knowledge exchange on common challenges (e.g., legal issues like GDPR/IPR), and coordinated development support. In particular, FIDELIS will help members implement best practices and standards, promote standardization and interoperability across repositories, as well as provide training and mentorship to repository staff. During 2025-2027, repositories can join the provisional network and benefit from pilot support offerings: test-drive of tools, services, and methodologies provided by project partners, with feedback used to refine later training and grant opportunities. In effect, FIDELIS connects research data repositories into a broader community, offering resources to build trustworthiness and ensuring their work is aligned with EOSC standards and services. Looking ahead, it is expected to strengthen the European preservation landscape by combining formal certification schemes with practical, network-based support.

Recommended further resources:

- Lin et al. (2020): [The TRUST Principles for digital repositories](#)
- DPC: [Audit and certification](#) in Digital Preservation Handbook
- EOSC EDEN T1.2 (2025): [M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes](#)

²⁹ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101188078> (accessed: 10 December 2025); for project outputs, see the Zenodo-Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/fidelis-project> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

5 Approaching Digital Long-Term Preservation on an Institutional Level

The implementation of a coherent approach to long-term preservation of digital research data within a repository requires careful considerations, assessments, and decision-making on an institutional level. This chapter aims to outline in an abstract way the aspects and topics which need to be considered in this process as well as how to approach the conceptualization of a preservation policy and the implementation of a digital preservation system.

5.1 Assessment and Clarification of Objectives, Capabilities, and Risks

The first step towards implementing or improving on existing long-term preservation approaches of digital research data in repositories is an assessment of the current set-up. Having a clear understanding and overview about the type of research data being kept (or willing to accept), the repository's user community and environment, available resources and capabilities as well as risks and threats to the digital objects of the repository's collection is essential. It serves as a basis for the decision-making process for the development and implementation of a coherent preservation policy and preservation planning. It is recommended to regularly revisit the following aspects in order to be able to adapt to changes over time and adjust the repository's preservation planning and workflows accordingly.

5.1.1 Defining the Scope of Collection

Clarifying the scope of the repository's collection is important for two reasons. Firstly, to align the scope of the collection to the repository's mission, defining what type of research data and from which scientific discipline the repository wants to be responsible for in the long term. Secondly, to be able to preserve digital research data in the long term and undertake preservation actions over time a certain degree of knowledge about the research data, its content, and the scientific domain it was created in, is required. Both strategies for content preservation, migration and emulation, need the ability to assess the results of undertaken preservation actions, making sure no significant properties or relevant content or functionalities are being lost in the process. Based on the repository's expertise and capabilities, assessing and defining the type and scope of research data the repository is capable of taking over responsibility for and preserve in the long term is essential.

5.1.2 Determining the Designated Community

Considerations and clarifications about the repository's primary user group, defined in the OAIS reference model as the designated community, is important for the development of a concrete preservation policy for several reasons. Scientific relevance of the research data to the repository's designated community might have an impact on the scope of the repository's collection policy, helping to determine which data to accept and which not.

More importantly though, determining the scope of the designated community and its knowledge base (e.g., domain knowledge, expected competencies on data handling and standards) has a direct impact on the concrete design and implementation of preservation planning within a repository. The designated community is the part of the repository's user group that is expected to independently understand the preserved research data without the need for any additional resources. Thus, the designated community's knowledge base should guide the decision-making processes regarding how research data (e.g., level of documentation, depth and structure of metadata, accepted file formats or file formats considered for migration) is being preserved within a repository.

The knowledge base of the designated community as well as the user expectations and requirements for reusability and interoperability of research data can change over time. Staying in touch with the designated community helps to monitor any relevant changes and adapt to these as needed.

5.1.3 Clarifying Capabilities and Portfolio of Services

Another factor to be considered is the question of what specific services for long-term preservation and levels of preservation the repository is willing and capable to offer. There is normally a variety of possible solution approaches to the challenges of digital long-term preservation and implementation strategies, depending on the type of data being preserved and the repository's capabilities and available resources. The assessment of the repository's capabilities and available resources, such as a sustainable funding framework, staff expertise, or IT capabilities, should serve as a basis for the decision-making process on the preservation services the repository is willing and capable to offer. Calculating the exact costs for digital long-term preservation can be challenging. Frameworks for modelling and projecting these costs offer a helpful orientation. E.g., the project 4C (Collaboration to Clarify the Costs of Curation³⁰), co-funded by the European Union, has developed and compiled models and materials on this topic as well as provides support with the platform Curation Costs Exchange³¹. Questions to be

³⁰ <https://www.4cproject.eu/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

³¹ <https://www.curationexchange.org/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

considered regarding the repository's service portfolio include e.g., guaranteed preservation and curation timeframes for deposited research data, levels of preservation offered (e.g., whether content preservation is being offered and which preservation strategy is being implemented), accepted and supported file formats and metadata standards, or available pipelines for the deposit of and access to research data.

5.1.4 Undertaking Risk Assessment and Risk Management

Assessing and managing risks and threats to the digital object is an integral part of digital long-term preservation and preservation planning, which repositories willing to take over long-term responsibility as designated curation institutions for research data have to address. As described in chapter 2, digital obsolescence, due to technological and cultural change over time, represents the biggest risk. Not addressing and having a valid preservation approach in place for digital obsolescence entails the risk of losing the ability to render and interpret the content of the digital object, thus losing the ability to offer meaningful access to the digital object in the future. Monitoring relevant technological and cultural changes as well as assessing the risks for the repository's collection resulting from those changes is essential to identify the point in time where preservation actions are required to be undertaken.

Further risks are dependent on the specific type of data being preserved in the repository as well as the organizational structure and institutional framework of the repository. Geospatial data for example often has a high degree of complexity, can reach significant data volume, or can be dependent on proprietary software and/or file formats, all posing potential risks to its preservation.³² On an institutional level factors such as a change in the funding framework, dependencies on single staff expertise or external service and system providers (e.g., for IT support or preservation systems), missing documentation or unclear responsibilities within the institution may pose risks to the ability to preserve research data in the long term. Developing an institutionalized framework for identifying and assessing specific risks to the repository's collection is an important part of risk management in the long-term preservation of digital research data.

In addition, geospatial data may carry critical dependencies that need preservation. For example, satellite sensor data often require calibration coefficients or reference measurements to remain interpretable, and simulation results depend on input datasets and configuration parameters (data lineage) that must accompany the preserved outputs. Repositories should capture or link such supplementary information so that preserved data can be correctly understood and reused in the future.

³² (Snow, 2023)

Recommended further resources:

- DPC (2024): [Rapid Assessment Model \(DPC RAM\). Version 3](#)
- Hein & Schmitt (2013): [Risk Management for Digital Long-Term Preservation Services](#)
- DPC: [Assessing the risks](#)
- DPC: [Risk and change management](#) in Digital Preservation Handbook

5.2 Formulating a Coherent Preservation Policy

Based on the assessment and clarification of the above-described aspects, the next step towards implementing long-term preservation approaches of digital research data in repositories is the development and formulation of a coherent preservation policy. Any institution dealing with long-term preservation will require a comprehensive set of policies, guidelines, and documentations outlining in detail roles, responsibilities, tasks, procedures, and workflows for specific areas, functions, and preservation activities within the repository (see also chapter 6). The preservation policy serves in this context as a high-level framework, outlining the overarching principles of the repository's preservation approach and functioning as a guide and reference document for the decision-making and implementation process of preservation activities within the repository. Taking the following aspects into consideration will help in developing and drafting a suitable preservation policy in line with the repository's mission, needs, and capabilities.

5.2.1 Target Audience

Before beginning to draft a preservation policy, it is important to consider and identify the target audience of the document. Firstly, it needs to be considered, which departments and individuals within the repository will have to work with the policy and rely on it in their preservation activities. Secondly, the question whether the document is intended to also address external stakeholders (e.g., funding entities, data users, data depositors) has to be made. This helps with adopting appropriate language and determining the background knowledge of the target audience, while not losing focus on the primary intent of the preservation policy as a high-level framework for preservation activities within the repository.

5.2.2 Scope and Relations to other Documents

The preservation policy is normally one document among many dealing with various aspects of digital long-term preservation and the overall operations within a repository. Thus, it is necessary to define the scope and level of detail of the policy as well as its relation to other

documents. It is recommended to focus in the preservation policy on the high-level principles guiding the preservation approach within the repository and outsource the more detailed day-to-day aspects of preservation activities into separate documents or procedure manuals.

Furthermore, there might be other high-level policies regarding the overall operations of the repository already in place (e.g., implementation of FAIR-principles) that need to be considered before drafting a preservation policy. Referencing those documents, where appropriate, helps to keep the preservation policy concise.

5.2.3 Inclusion of Relevant Stakeholders

Developing and drafting an impactful preservation policy, which is viable and implementable within the framework of the repository's environment, capabilities, and organizational structure, requires the inclusion of relevant stakeholders. On the one hand, this includes relevant departments or individuals within the repository, who will be involved in the preservation activities or will be required to provide technical infrastructure and IT services. On the other hand, involving and getting input from external stakeholders, especially the repository's designated community in the role of data producers and data users, helps to align the preservation policy to the broader needs and requirements of the scientific community. It is advisable to allocate sufficient time for this process of engagement and acquiring input and reviews from internal and external stakeholders.

5.2.4 Content and Structure

The structure and content of a preservation policy naturally depend on the repository's specific circumstances and framework as well as the services and levels of preservation the repository is willing to offer. The following points outline briefly the fundamental aspects that are recommended to be covered in a preservation policy.

- **Purpose and aim:** This section establishes the motivation and reasoning for developing the policy and committing to the long-term preservation of digital research data. Embedding the preservation activities in the organization's overarching mission or scientific landscape helps to justify and explain the necessity for the preservation efforts.
- **Scope of collection:** Here the scope of the repository's collection is defined, describing what type of data the repository is willing or according to its mission allowed to accept as well as explaining the selection criteria (e.g., relevance for or origin from a specific scientific discipline, creation within specific institutions, quality specifications) for acceptance.
- **Standards:** This segment outlines the overarching standards or models (e.g., OAIS reference model, PREMIS metadata standard) on which the repository's preservation

approach is based on. Obtained certifications as trustworthy repositories (e.g., CoreTrustSeal) can be included as well.

- **Preservation strategies and principles:** The preservation policy should include an explanation of the main preservation strategies and guiding principles adopted in the repository's approach to digital long-term preservation.
- **Services and levels of preservation:** In this section, the preservation services and levels of preservation offered by the repository can be outlined in more detail, e.g., guaranteed preservation and curation timeframes.
- **Roles and responsibilities:** Having roles and responsibilities for specific preservation activities clearly defined is essential. Besides contributing to responsible and efficient management, it helps to mitigate the risks associated with long-term preservation of digital research data.
- **Sustainability:** Operating preservation activities and services for digital research data in a sustainable way is based on the availability of sufficient resources for expert staff and technical infrastructure. While acquiring open-ended funding is often difficult in the scientific landscape, demonstrating the ability for sustainable operations for the foreseeable future is important and might be helpful in securing ongoing funding for the repository's preservation effort. Having an exit and/or succession strategy in place ensures the preserved data is not being lost in case the repository has to stop operations.

5.2.5 Adoption, Dissemination, and Implementation

The next steps after the development of the preservation policy are its adoption, dissemination, and implementation within the repository. Adoption by the relevant governing bodies provides institutional support for the adopted preservation approach. Dissemination ensures awareness and understanding of the repository's preservation approach across relevant staff and stakeholders. Depending on already existing preservation efforts within the repository, the implementation of the preservation policy into the day-to-day operations can be a complex and lengthy process. Workflows and procedures might need to be developed or newly created, along with supporting documentation and guidelines. Implementation plans can be a helpful tool in this process.

5.2.6 Transparency and Publication

Transparency about the preservation principles and approaches adopted by the repository is a crucial element in developing and maintaining trust of the repository's user community, as outlined in the TRUST principles and certification frameworks for trustworthy digital

repositories (e.g., CoreTrustSeal). Thus, in general it is advisable to publish the preservation policy, or, if there are valid reasons not to do so, provide a concise publicly accessible version or summary of the policy.

5.2.7 Regular Reviews

A preservation policy should be reviewed at regular, predefined intervals to ensure it remains up-to-date and effective. These reviews provide an opportunity to assess whether the repository's preservation approach and principles keep up with the changes in technology as well as evolving community expectations and user needs.

Recommended further resources:

- DPC (2023): [Digital Preservation Policy Toolkit. Version 2](#)
- DCC: [Guidance and tools for creating policies](#)
- nestor (2024): [Guidelines for the creation of an institutional policy on digital preservation](#)

5.3 Implementing a Digital Preservation System

Managing digital data within a repository involves the usage of one or various information management systems. Digital preservation systems might include the general functionalities of an information management system, but also provide essential functions for managing and conducting preservation activities within the repository. A digital preservation system can be defined as "the applications and tools used to preserve digital content that enact processes such as ingest, storage, preservation, and access."³³

In the last two decades, many digital preservation systems have been developed, claiming to allow for an OAIS-compliant preservation environment. The Community Owned Digital Preservation Tool Registry (COPTR)³⁴ offers an overview of existing digital preservation systems.

Repositories aiming to introduce a digital preservation system have three options to choose from:

- Developing their own preservation system
- Using an open-source solution

³³ <https://www.dpconline.org/docs/digital-preservation/procurement-toolkit/2581-core-requirements-for-a-digital-preservation-system-v1/file> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

³⁴ https://coptr.digipres.org/Preservation_System (accessed: 10 December 2025)

- Procuring a commercial/proprietary solution

Which of the three options is best suited to the repository's needs and requirements depends on factors such as the availability of expert staff (e.g., software developers), financial capabilities, or the willingness to be dependent on third-party suppliers. Considerations regarding the overall preservation framework adopted at the repository, such as implemented preservation strategies, the type of data being preserved, or interoperability with standards (e.g., metadata standards) and systems already in use at the repository, play a crucial role as well.

Regardless of which option is being assessed most suitable for the repository, the digital preservation system should be able to fulfill some core specifications and functions. The Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) has compiled a set of ten core requirements for a digital preservation system³⁵, which are reproduced here:

- The system must precisely record and manage the integrity and authenticity of the digital content and metadata it holds. It must use checksums to verify that digital content has not accidentally or maliciously been changed over time and metadata to record any actions enacted on the content.
- The system must have a comprehensive data model that enables the complex structure of digital objects to be captured on ingest and accurately represented over time as they are managed and preserved.
- The system must provide a clear exit strategy to other systems, without vendor lock in. This must ensure that the inevitable migration to a future digital preservation system is possible. It should also minimize the effort and risk involved in such a migration.
- The system must enable authentic digital content and metadata to be ingested.
- The system must have the facility to assess the characteristics of ingested digital content and record them in associated metadata.
- The system must support replication and storage management. The system must have the ability to store multiple copies of ingested digital content on different storage systems in different geographical locations.
- The system should support preservation planning, including risk assessment, and the design and testing of plans to preserve digital content.
- The system should support preservation actions that fulfil preservation plans designed to mitigate identified preservation risks.
- The system must support the management of digital content and metadata over time.

³⁵ See in more detail: <https://www.dpconline.org/docs/digital-preservation/procurement-toolkit/2581-core-requirements-for-a-digital-preservation-system-v1/file> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

- The system must enable the controlled discovery of, and access to, digital content and metadata.

Recommended further resources:

- DPC (2022): [Digital Preservation Procurement Toolkit. Version 2](#)
- DPC (2022): [Core Requirements for a Digital Preservation System](#)
- [Community Owned digital Preservation Tool Registry \(COPTR\)](#)

6 Procedures and Workflows for Handling Long-Term Preservation within Repositories

Long-term preservation can be understood as a sequence of interlinked processes rather than a single technical act. Effective practice often follows the OAIS reference model (see chapter 3.2.), which defines functions from ingest through access. The aim of this chapter is to provide a pragmatic overview of these functions, focusing on the workflow character of digital preservation and the key decisions that repository providers face at each stage. It does not attempt to cover all operational details or discipline-specific best practices, but instead outlines common steps, typical challenges, and pointers to standards and tools that can be applied in different contexts. To build and demonstrate trust (see chapter 4) repositories should document policies, workflows, and procedures across the preservation lifecycle. In particular, the OAIS reference model requires repositories to “negotiate for and accept appropriate information... follow documented policies” and make data available to a designated community.³⁶ Following this logic, the chapter describes each stage as a process with objectives, points of attention, and strategies for addressing potential risks. The subchapters are organized accordingly:

- **Appraisal:** defining scope and selection criteria, assessing value and risks.
- **Data acquisition and legal agreements:** formalizing submission (or deposit) agreements, rights, and responsibilities.
- **Data transfer and ingest:** ensuring secure transfer, fixity, and packaging of Submission Information Packages (SIPs) into Archival Information Packages (AIPs).
- **Preservation actions:** monitoring integrity, managing obsolescence, and planning preservation steps.
- **Access:** creating Dissemination Information Packages (DIP) and ensuring discoverability, usability, and compliance with rights.

³⁶(The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems, 2024b, p. 3-1)

Together, these sections present the preservation workflow as a structured process: setting goals, identifying challenges, embedding requirements into organizational and legal frameworks, and drawing on standards and tools to implement solutions.

The DCC Curation Lifecycle Model (Fig. 2) provides a concise illustration and high-level overview of the stages needed for long-term preservation. Repository providers can use and adapt this model e.g., for defining specific roles and responsibilities within the organization.

Figure 2: DCC Curation Lifecycle Model³⁷

³⁷ (Higgins, 2008, p. 136)

6.1 Appraisal

Appraisal is the evaluation of incoming data to decide if (and how) to preserve it³⁸. Its primary goal is to determine the lasting value of the material and its alignment with the repository's mission and collection policy³⁹. For example, DIN 31644 requires that the repository has clearly defined criteria for appraisal of digital data and a defined user community. Appraisal criteria typically include scientific or historical value, uniqueness, and compliance with legal or ethical constraints (e.g., intellectual property rights (IPR), privacy and personal protection rights). Appraisal should be transparent and documented: all decisions (accept/reject, with reasons) must be recorded in the repository's preservation metadata. Records of appraisal decisions themselves serve as metadata to justify why data were preserved or not.

In practice, appraisal is often followed or accompanied by pre-ingest checks to ensure that selected data can be preserved in a sustainable way within the repository's preservation framework. These checks focus less on the lasting value and more on immediate readiness, confirming file formats against approved lists, assessing metadata completeness, and clarifying rights and licenses needed for long-term preservation and reuse. Separating these two dimensions—appraisal of the lasting value and technical/rights validation—helps to keep decision-making structured.

- **Define scope and criteria:** Ensure the content of the offered research data falls within the repository's mission and collection policy. Check funding or regulatory requirements and discipline-specific norms.
- **Assess value and risks:** Evaluate scientific importance, uniqueness, or legal obligations (e.g., mandated retention). Verify Intellectual Property Rights and licenses, as well as obtain permission to preserve and provide access if needed.
- **Conduct pre-ingest checks:** Ensure that essential descriptive and technical metadata⁴⁰ (e.g., Dublin Core, ISO 19115 for geodata, PREMIS for preservation metadata) as well as relevant documentation are provided. Confirm metadata sufficiency for discoverability, preservation, and future reuse.
- **Document decisions:** Record appraisal outcomes and reasoning in the metadata. E.g., note format suitability or reasons for rejecting a dataset. Decision documentation is critical for audit trails.

³⁸ (The National Archives, 2022)

³⁹ Separate Guidelines on the topic of "Appraisal of ESS data for long-term preservation" will be published by the NFDI4Earth measure M2.4 in early 2026. A workshop on this topic (NFDI4Earth-Workshop zur Entwicklung von Kriterien für die Bewertung der Archivwürdigkeit von Daten der Bio-/Geowissenschaften) has been held at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Potsdam, Deutsches GeoForschungszentrum GFZ on 14th December 2023. The results of this workshop are published on Zenodo: (zu Castell, et al., 2024)

⁴⁰ (Calanag, Sugimoto, & Tabata, 2001)

- **Communicate with depositor:** If data do not meet criteria (e.g., unsupported file formats, incomplete metadata), inform the producer and discuss remediation or alternative repositories.

6.2 Data Acquisition and Legal Agreements

If the outcome of the appraisal process is positive, the next step is to formalize terms and conditions for preservation in form of a submission (or deposit) agreement between the repository and the data depositor. The central goal of this stage is to establish a clear legal and organizational framework that allows the repository to preserve and disseminate the data in line with its policies. The main challenge lies in ensuring that rights are unambiguous. Without explicit permission, essential preservation actions such as file format migration or providing access in the long term may not be legally possible.

In practice, repositories address this by negotiating deposit agreements with data depositors or using standardized licenses. These agreements define the scope of the transfer, set out any restrictions (e.g., embargo periods, confidentiality clauses), and confirm that the depositor grants the necessary rights for preservation and reuse. Standardized templates and guidance documents help to streamline the process and reduce negotiation overhead. They also specify what accompanying documentation must be provided (e.g., file manifests, readme files, metadata) and which file formats suitable for long-term preservation are accepted by the repository. For ESS data, repositories typically encourage the use of open, self-describing file formats such as NetCDF or HDF5, which are widely adopted for climate, weather, and geospatial datasets. Favoring these standard file formats (and associated tools) facilitates long-term preservation because they embed rich metadata and are well-supported by the community, ensuring that large multidimensional data (e.g., model outputs, satellite imagery) remain accessible and interpretable over time.

- **Negotiate deposit terms:** Agree on the scope of data to be transferred and any conditions (e.g., embargoes, use restrictions). Ensure the data depositor understands what rights they grant (e.g., allow repository to migrate or disseminate data).
- **Use standard agreements:** Adopt templates ensuring minimum rights required for long-term preservation are secured.
- **Gather documentation:** Request detailed metadata, documentation of data structure (e.g., codebooks, schemas), and provenance information from the data producer.
- **Acknowledge deposit:** Send a formal receipt and summary of the agreement to the data depositor. If any deficiencies are identified (e.g., missing metadata), follow up promptly.

By addressing legal clarity upfront, repositories create a secure foundation for all subsequent preservation actions.

6.3 Data Transfer and Ingest

During transfer and ingest, the repository assumes technical custody of the data. This process begins with the preparation and receipt of Submission Information Packages (SIPs), which are structured containers of the digital object and associated metadata provided by the data producer. SIPs may follow packaging specifications such as BagIt (RFC 8493)⁴¹ or repository-defined submission profiles. The repository should ensure that the SIP includes all agreed components (data files, metadata, and documentation).

For the transfer itself, security and integrity are paramount. Depending on data volume and sensitivity, methods may include physical media (with chain-of-custody documentation) or secure network protocols (SFTP, HTTPS). Before and after transfer, fixity information (checksums like SHA-256) must be computed and verified against manifests to detect any corruption or transmission errors. The SIP should initially be quarantined until its integrity, safety, and completeness are confirmed.

- **Transfer method:** Choose transfer means (e.g., shipped drive, upload portal, FTP) that are appropriate for the data's size and sensitivity. Record all files in a manifest before transfer. If using BagIt, ensure it follows the specification with a file directory and checksum files.
- **Fixity verification:** Compute checksums on all files prior to transfer and validate them upon receipt. This ensures data integrity and provides an audit trail.
- **Format identification:** Utilize format identification tools (e.g., DROID⁴², Siegfried⁴³) to detect file formats and versions. Record identification results as part of the ingest documentation.

Following transfer, the ingest process transforms SIPs into Archival Information Packages (AIPs). This involves enriching metadata, verifying file formats, and structuring content to align with repository preservation policies. Some repositories use workflow-supporting tools to automate parts of this process. For example, tools such as Archivematica⁴⁴ can assist in managing ingest workflows by applying micro-services for tasks like checksum validation, format identification, and packaging content with METS⁴⁵-structured metadata. However, the choice of workflow

⁴¹ (Kunze, Littman, Madden, Scancella, & Adams, 2018)

⁴² <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/information-management/manage-information/preserving-digital-records/droid/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

⁴³ <https://itforarchivists.com/siegfried> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

⁴⁴ <https://www.archivematica.org/en/docs/archivematica-1.17/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

⁴⁵ Metadata Encoding & Transmission Standard, see: <https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

tools should reflect the repository's context. Archivematica represents one implementation among several possible approaches.

Repositories may choose to normalize file formats during ingest according to its policy, preservation planning, and submission agreement (e.g., converting proprietary file formats to open standards). Such normalization actions should be documented, but repositories should avoid unnecessary conversions. Using standards for preservation metadata such as PREMIS⁴⁶ can support this documentation.

- **Ingest workflow:** Define and execute ingest procedures to validate, enrich, and structure SIP contents into AIPs. Select tools that support your repository's scale and technical needs.
- **Normalization (if needed):** Apply file format normalization during ingest only where policy or preservation risk assessments justify it. Record actions in preservation metadata.
- **Document ingest:** Maintain records of ingest processes, including validation logs, file inventories, and tool versions. This documentation becomes part of the AIP to support transparency and future audits.

The resulting AIP should be securely integrated into the repository's storage infrastructure, with all provenance and processing documentation preserved for long-term reference.

6.4 Preservation Actions

Long-term preservation requires active monitoring and systematic intervention to ensure the ongoing integrity and accessibility of digital holdings⁴⁷. Repositories must implement strategies for redundancy, fixity verification, storage health monitoring, and format sustainability.

Multiple redundant copies of each Archival Information Package (AIP) should be maintained across geographically and technologically diverse storage environments. Regularly scheduled fixity checks are essential to detect bit-level corruption or data loss. Tools supporting automated fixity verification—such as checksum audit scripts or workflow platforms—can assist in these processes, but repositories may employ any mechanism suited to their scale and infrastructure.

- **Regular fixity checks:** Periodically recompute and verify checksums against original values to identify integrity issues. Establish procedures to address discrepancies through restoration from verified copies.

⁴⁶ (PREMIS Editorial Committee, 2015)

⁴⁷ (Becker, et al., 2009)

- **Storage monitoring:** Continuously monitor storage media and infrastructure health, including hardware diagnostics and environmental factors. Plan for proactive media replacement before end-of-life and maintain up-to-date backups.

Preservation also involves managing the risks associated with file format obsolescence. Repositories should maintain an inventory of file formats recorded during ingest and track their sustainability using external file format registries like PRONOM⁴⁸ or discipline-specific lists. If file formats are identified as at-risk of becoming obsolete or out of use, the repository must assess appropriate actions, such as migration to more sustainable file formats or implementing emulation strategies.

Platforms offering Format Policy Registries (FPR), can aid in managing file format-related policies. However, repositories should determine file format strategies based on their specific needs, using tools and workflows that align with their preservation objectives.

- **File format obsolescence management:** Monitor the sustainability of file formats using reliable registries and community resources. Develop and execute migration or emulation strategies as necessary and document undertaken actions.
- **Update preservation plans:** Review and update preservation strategies periodically to reflect technological developments, new standards, or changes in repository resources. Maintain a Technology Watch function to stay informed on preservation trends and identify risks stemming from digital obsolescence.

All preservation actions—such as fixity checks, format migrations, storage incidents, and corrective measures—should be documented as part of the AIP's provenance record. Preservation metadata standards (e.g., PREMIS) can support this documentation.

The goal of preservation actions is to ensure that AIPs remain accessible, trustworthy, and reusable over the long term, irrespective of technological evolution or infrastructure changes.

6.5 Access

Finally, preserved data must be made accessible in a controlled and discoverable way. A distinction is important here. Repositories typically publish metadata records openly to enable discovery and citation, while access to the underlying data objects depends on legal, ethical, or policy constraints. Assigning persistent identifiers (PIDs) to each dataset or collection is best practice: DOIs, Handles or ARKs provide long-lasting references even if data is moved. Persistent IDs aid citation and track usage. Ensure rich metadata is published (via e.g., a data catalog) so users can find the data and understand its context. This includes descriptive

⁴⁸ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/> (accessed: 10 December 2025)

metadata (e.g., Dublin Core, ISO 19115), license/rights metadata, and links to documentation. The NFDI4Earth created white paper “Recommendations for Earth System Sciences Metadata Provision”, published in a revised version in early 2026, serves as a helpful orientation on this topic.⁴⁹

When users request data, the repository’s preservation system delivers a Dissemination Information Package (DIP)—essentially the subset of the AIP for access. Tools can automatically generate DIPs containing access-friendly copies (normalized formats, thumbnails, etc.) and upload them to access systems. In simpler setups, the repository might serve the original files directly with an accompanying metadata file. Always include clear usage statements (e.g., Creative Commons license) and citation instructions. Access interfaces (web portals, APIs, or integration with systems like Dataverse, AtoM, or DSpace) should support search by metadata and linkage back to the index entries. In all cases, respect any agreed access restrictions or embargoes.

- **Persistent identifiers:** Mint PIDs for datasets so users and systems have stable links. Register these in global resolvers (e.g., DataCite, Handle.net).
- **Metadata exposure:** Publish rich metadata (including authors, dates, formats, keywords) alongside data. Adopt metadata standards relevant to the repository’s discipline-specific domain.
- **Create DIPs (access packages):** Provide downloadable bundles with necessary files and metadata. E.g., Archivematica’s access function can package and export DIPs for systems like AtoM or Binder.
- **Access platforms:** Use data repositories or portals (with search and API capabilities) that allow users to browse and retrieve datasets. Ensure the interfaces display citations, license terms, and contact information.
- **Monitor usage and feedback:** Track downloads and citations. Update records if error reports or new metadata are provided by users.

⁴⁹ (Bernard, et al., 2026)

7 Outlook

Ensuring the long-term preservation of valuable digital research data within repositories is a task in perpetuity. It requires continuous monitoring of changes and developments over time and the adjustment of the implemented preservation approach accordingly. To stay informed about relevant developments in community needs, requirements, and standards as well as evolving preservation standards, trends, and best practices it is imperative to connect with practitioners, stakeholders, and communities engaged in digital long-term preservation. Depending on the repository's capacities and responsibilities, networking with national (e.g., NFDI, nestor), European (e.g., EOSC), and global (e.g., Digital Preservation Coalition) initiatives is highly recommended.

Furthermore, to move towards a more sustainable data culture in ESS and science in general, addressing and improving the funding framework for repositories engaged in digital long-term preservation is necessary. Dependencies on short-term and/or project-based funding timeframes need to be minimized. They are a significant obstacle for establishing and maintaining sustainable long-term preservation services in repositories as designated curation institutions. Securing a reliable and predictable funding framework in the long term for trusted entities is essential for a successful long-term preservation of digital research data in repositories. Thus, it is important to raise awareness of this issue and advocate for sustainable solutions with policy-makers and decision-makers shaping the future funding landscape in science.

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